

THE SPECIFICITY OF THE INFORMATION ECONOMY AND THE DEVELOPMENT OF ICT IN UZBEKISTAN

Ismailov Janibek Aktamovich

Jizzakh State Pedagogical University teacher

Annotation. At present, the development of new technologies, along with the development of information and communication technologies (ICT), creates opportunities for the rapid delivery and exchange of information, money and other resources, regardless of distance and time. In this article, the process of ICT development in Uzbekistan and its impact on other industries will be discussed.

Key words: information technologies, information economy, industry, ICT, telecommunication, system.

The profound and radical changes taking place in connection with the transition to an informed economy are leading to a number of problems and contradictions. Such problems can be attributed to the variability and instability of economic life, which has arisen due to globalization and informatization of various spheres of society, and which requires a comprehensive study and a comprehensive approach. Of these, the growing impact of education, ICT, scientific and innovative activities on society, the state and the economy, as well as the qualitatively new features of their activities. Therefore, how the theory of modern economics defines the contradictions in the life of society and how its theoretical content is reflected in the modern stage of the world economy and to show the specifics of the information economy is one of the most important issues today.

The development of ICT in Uzbekistan is carried out on the basis of the Comprehensive Development Program of the National Information and Communication System of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2013-2020. Successful monitoring of the implementation of state programs for the development of ICT is a guarantee of building an effective system of indicators for the formation of an informed economy. The level of formation of an informed economy in Uzbekistan, as in any other country, the introduction and development of modern ICT, indicators of the introduction of research into the economy and the share of services in GDP. Given the lack of in-depth research on the information economy in Uzbekistan, it is important to study and conduct research on this topic.

The analysis of the content of the information economy is reflected in the scientific works of such scientists as M. Porat, D. Bell, U. Dayzard, M. Castels, M. Connorz, U. Martin, A. Norman, and the category of the informed economy itself is

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-4, ISSUE-3

reflected in science in 1976. introduced by the American economist M. Porat [1, p.71]. Thanks to the Spanish-American economist M. Castels' monograph "The Information Age: Economy, Society, and Culture" published in 1996-1998, the term "information economy" became widespread. According to the criteria of time, the formation of the theory of information economy can be divided into three periods: the emergence of an informed economy and the identification of trends in the development of a new phenomenon (1960-1970); rapid development of the information economy in developed countries (1980–1990); to study the theory of information economy in relation to the knowledge economy (since 2000). In general, economic theory does not have a single concept or definition of an informed economy, but there are different approaches to it in the scientific literature. Nevertheless, many studies distinguish three main groups of criteria specific to the information economy [2]. The first group includes economic criteria, which describe the share of society in the gross national product (GNP) created in the field of information. The main problem of this approach is that the country faces certain difficulties in determining the contribution of the information sector in GDP. The second group includes social criteria. They use information products, determining the share of the population engaged in the production of information media and the provision of information services. The third group includes technological criteria that define the information economy, ie in terms of the spread of information technology (IT) in society.

At present, our society is experiencing the emergence of an informed economy. At the same time, it should be noted that it is characterized by uncertainty and high dynamics of development in the future. In a broad sense, the scientific literature considers the information economy as a branch of economics that studies the impact of information on economic decisions [3]. M. Castels points out that the term "information society" is not perfect and does not reflect all the peculiarities of the new system. According to him, the term "informational economy" can have a more accurate definition [4, pp. 42-43]. BV Korneychuk, on the other hand, uses two different concepts to express his views on the term information economy. In the first, he describes the information economy as a stage in the development of a civilization where creative labor and information resources predominate. In the second, the information economy is considered as the economic theory of the informed society or the theory of the informed economy [5].

In addition, in a sense, the following definition explains the object of research: Informed economy is the basis of post-industrial society, where information is the main resource of production and the main role in the structure of employment is occupied by mental labor. is a philosophical-economic term that defines the specific

type of economy occupied by the workers employed. [6, p. 20]. A modern scientific work describes: "The information economy is a stage of development of productive forces, which includes the role of knowledge and information in society, the growing share of information products and services in GDP, information and communication technologies, human interaction. effective information exchange, the creation of a global information space that allows them to access global information resources and meet their social and personal needs "[7, pp. 23–24]. It should be noted that the comparative analysis of the information economy by country is associated with the development of the following new trends [8, p. 268]:

- differentiation of traditional and information economy;
- the formation of certain contradictions between the sectors of the information economy and the economy of the industrial era;
- increasingly penetrating the globalized economy.

Currently, in the world practice, various rating indicators are used to assess the level of development of the information economy, but it should be noted that the relevant concepts and statistics are not yet fully formed. In general, the development of the country's information economy is associated with the following indices [9]: innovation (knowledge economy - Knowledge Economy Index (KEI), innovation - The Global Innovation Index (GII); e-government readiness - United Nations e-Government Readiness Index (UNEGRI); ICT market. The value of the e-government index is calculated based on online participation in government networks, the current state of the country's telecommunications infrastructure and human capital development indicators. An important issue is the development of indicators of informatization and methods of its application in practice. A number of indicators can be cited, the most important of which are:

- ✓ Technological equipment indicator, American scientists F. Rodriguez and E. Dj. Developed by Wilsons (Maryland). This indicator is designed to assess and measure the state of development of ICTs in different countries. Personal computers, mobile phones, Internet hosts, fax machines, televisions, etc. are used to calculate indicators;
- ✓ An indicator of communication transparency, it was developed by experts from the US National Science Foundation to assess the level of use of ICT in the interaction between the population, business and government [4, p. 235]. This indicator is of particular importance for state, regional and local government and serves to show the level of application of modern ICT by the authorities;
- ✓ An indicator of the status of an informed society is developed and used by the World Times and IDC. This indicator, in general, reflects the level of creation,

use of information technologies, their spread and determines their level. The specificity of the development of ICT in Uzbekistan can be characterized by the fact that it consists of several stages:

1. The initial stage of development - (2000-2002). Period of improvement of public administration through the gradual introduction of ICT;
2. The second stage - (2003–2007) the period of adoption of the main legal and regulatory documents for the widespread introduction of ICT;
3. The third stage - (2008-2012) the period of active implementation of internal information systems and software products in government agencies, the beginning of the provision of information and electronic information services;
4. The fourth stage - (from 2012 to the present) is a period of further improvement of the public administration structure.

It should be noted that the National Information and Communication System Development Strategy, which covers all areas of ICT development and is being implemented, shows an active positive growth trend. This means that the share of the informed economy has a significant impact on the economy as a whole. In short, the widespread and active introduction of ICT has led to structural imbalances in the labor market, the transformation of the role of information, the growth of the dependence of one industry on another, the growing role of scientific research in production and services. Analyzing and monitoring its impact with this in mind, it is necessary to conduct research on the formation and development of a large-scale information economy in Uzbekistan.

References

1. Porat V. The Information Economy Definition and Measurement. Washington DC: US Dept of Commerce, 1977. R. 240 .;
2. Tagarov B. J. Sovremennyye podhody k opredeleniyu kriteriev informatsionnoy ekonomiki.// Baikal research journal. - Irkutsk, 2012. - №4.S.3. [Electronic resource].
URL: <http://elibrary.ru/download/30837991.pdf> .(Data obrashcheniya 27.12.2015).
3. Letunova O. V. Filosofsko-metodologicheskiy aspekt proekta informatsionnoy ekonomiki.//Gramota. - Tambov, 2011. - №6 (12). - C. 115. [Electronic resource].
URL .: www.gramota.net/materiaW3/2011/6-2/29.html (Data obrashcheniya 27.12.2015).
4. Kastels M. Informatsionnaya epoch: ekonomika, obshchestvo i kultura / [Per. s angl., under nauch. ed. O. I. Shkaratana]. - M .: GUVShE, 2000. - 608 p.
5. Aktamovich, Ismailov Janibek. "BO 'LAJAK TEXNOLOGIK TA'LIM O

‘QITUCHILARINING KASB-HUNARGA YO ‘NALTIRISHDAGI MUAMMO VA YECHIMLARI." Journal of Science-Innovative Research in Uzbekistan 1.8 (2023): 647-650.

6. Burxonov, R., Ismoilov, J., & Mavlonov, E. (2022). TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARNI JORIY ETISHNING PEDAGOGIK ASOSLARI. Физико-технологического образование, (3).

7. Malikovich, Egamov Sul-tonjon. "VIZUALIZALANGAN MUHITDA DASTURLASH ASOSLARINI O'QITISH METODIKASINI TAKMILLATISH".

8. Malikovich, Sul-tonjon Egamov. "3O'LCHAMLI MODELLAR YARATISH VA ULARNI O'QITISH METODIKASI." Proceedings of International Educators Conference. Vol. 1. No. 3. 2022

9. XALIKOV, Akbar, Sul-tonjon EGAMOV, va Jahongir NORMATOV. «Grafik axborot tushunchasi va uning mohiyati». (2022).

10. XALIKOV, Akbar, Sul-tonjon EGAMOV, va Jahongir NORMATOV. «Grafik axborot tushunchasi va uning mohiyati». (2022).

11. Egamov, Sul-ton. "O'quv jarayoniga zamonaviy innovatsion texnologiyalarni joriy etish: muammo va yechimlar." Архив Научных Публикаций JSPI (2020).

12. Egamov, S. (2020). EPRA International Journal of Research and Development (IJRD). Архив Научных Публикаций JSPI.

13. Akbar, Xoliqov va Egamov Sul-ton. "Bulutli texnologiya." Galaxy xalqaro fanlararo tadqiqot jurnali 9.12 (2021): 458-460.

14. Rahmatov, A., Buribayev, B., Buriboyev, A., Otabekov, A., & Egamov, S. (2020). ABOUT PROBLEMS OF MATHEMATICAL MODELING OF DEVELOPMENT OF CHILDREN'S SPORTS IN REGIONS. Архив Научных Публикаций JSPI.

15. Korneychuk B. V. Informatsionnaya ekonomika: uchebnoe posobie. - SPb. : Peter, 2006. - 400 p.

16. Nikolaeva T. P. Informatsionnaya ekonomika i tendentsii ee razvitiya: dis. d-ra. econ. nauk: 08.00.01. - SPb., 1999. - 20 p. 3).

17. Nikitenkova M. A. Informatsionnaya struktura SShA: gosudarstvo i ry-nok / RAN. In-t SSHA and Canada. M. : Academia, 2009. - 298 p.

18. Boboxujaev Sh. I., Otakuzieva Z. M. Informatsionnaya ekonomika: mirovye tendentsii i spetsifika razvitiya v Uzbekistane. Innovative economy and social infrastructure. Sbornik nauchnyx statey. 2-ya chast. - T. : LESSON PRESS. 2015. - 308 c.

19. Lemeshchenko P. S., Shumskix E. V. Informatsionnaya ekonomika: mirovye tendentsii i spetsifika razvitiya v Respublike Belarus. // Nauchnye trudy Donetskogo natsionalnogo teh-nicheskogo universiteta. Series: ekonomicheskaya. -

Donetsk, 2014. - №1. - p.163. [Electronic resource].

URL . : <http://elibrary.ru/download/49985787.pdf> .

(Data obrashcheniya 27.12.2015).

20. Important steps of democratic transformations. National information agency of

Uzbekistan. [Electronic resource]. URL . : <http://uza.uz/ru/society/vazhnaya-stupen-demokraticeskikh-preobrazovaniy-12-11-2015> .

(Data obrashcheniya 27.12.2015).

21. Source: Statistical data in the National information-search system

www.uz. Open portal of the Republic of Uzbekistan. 01.07.2015 [Electronic resource]. URL . : <http://data.gov.uz/ru/datasets/326>.

